

LIFE RIPARIAS

Sharing invasive alien species data: why and how?

In action A.1 (“Improving data flow for early warning and rapid response”) of the LIFE RIPARIAS project, we will harmonise and aggregate data sources for new and emerging invasive alien species (IAS) in Belgium. Data harmonisation will be achieved by publishing data from individual sources to the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) (A.1.3). Subsequently, the bulk of standardised data will be extracted from GBIF to feed the LIFE RIPARIAS database and early alert web application (A.1.2).

In this document, we describe:

- the benefits of making biodiversity (IAS) data open
- why we use GBIF as a data infrastructure and aggregator
- what to do with personal and non-validated data
- the minimal information needed from data providers to allow an efficient harmonisation of data sources

1. The LIFE RIPARIAS data flow: an integrated approach

Before we describe the benefits of open data and the use of GBIF as an aggregator, we here shortly resume upon the LIFE RIPARIAS data flow. Field observations are typically stored in databases managed by each project partner. The objective of the LIFE RIPARIAS data flow is to aggregate all observations in a single RIPARIAS database, available for anyone to consult. To achieve this goal, we standardise each data source to the [Darwin Core \(DwC\) standard](#) (“data mapping”) and publish the standardised data openly to GBIF. These standardised data can then be extracted from GBIF to feed the RIPARIAS aggregated database, which will be used for the website and the early warning system.

Figure 1: The LIFE RIPARIAS integrated approach.

2. Why open data?

Sharing biodiversity data provides many benefits to biodiversity. Open data:

- supports transparent, evidence-based policy,
- is more impactful, since data can be used by for many use cases,

- is easier to engage with,
- is more scalable (e.g. can answer more complex questions than for which data were collected),
- requires less complex infrastructure (e.g. no authentication),
- stimulates collaboration,
- is more and more a requirement,
- increases your visibility, through citations and acknowledgements.

A remarkable global effort has been made to make raw biodiversity data accessible to the broad public. As a result, a great number of open data platforms have emerged. The portal GBIF acts as an important data aggregation platform from these various initiatives.

3. Why use GBIF?

GBIF is an **international network** and **data infrastructure** funded by the world's governments since 2001. It has a long history in the sharing, use and reuse of open-access biodiversity data and today gives access to close to two billion species occurrence records. GBIF day-to-day operations and development are managed by the GBIF secretariat in Copenhagen, but its work programme is decided upon by the Governing Board, where each GBIF participant country is represented. Belgium is represented by the Belgian Biodiversity Platform.

Data are not "uploaded" to GBIF, but made accessible online, typically via a GBIF Integrated Publishing Toolkit (IPT), hosted by e.g. the [Belgian Biodiversity Platform](#) and [INBO](#). This act is called "data publishing" and it is where a dataset is standardised to a common format, documented with metadata and assigned an open licence. By registering a dataset, GBIF knows of its existence and will make it available on its central portal and web services. This publication workflow is also how data can be updated or if necessary removed from GBIF. By publishing data sources to GBIF, we also **increase their use and long-term sustainability**: they are available to everyone and will remain so even after the LIFE RIPARIAS project.

The GBIF network combines data sources through the use of **data standards**, the most important one being the [Darwin Core Standard](#) or simply Darwin Core. This is an "evolving community-developed biodiversity standard" that offers a stable framework for compiling biodiversity data from variable sources. Publishing data to GBIF thus involves transforming source data to Darwin Core. Once created, this transformation is best stored as a script (e.g. a SQL view), so that new or updated source data can automatically be transformed to Darwin Core.

The LIFE RIPARIAS aggregated database will extract IAS data published to GBIF (under LIFE RIPARIAS and other sources) on a daily basis. Thanks to the GBIF facilities (data download and [web services](#)) and the fact that the data are all formatted the same way, this process is fairly simple and can be **fully automated**. The LIFE RIPARIAS early alert system will be built on top of this aggregated database.

As a LIFE RIPARIAS partner, the Open Science Lab for Biodiversity (OSCIBIO) from the Research Institute for Nature and Forest (INBO) offers **assistance** during the data publication process to GBIF. However, the ultimate, long-term goal is to **empower** data providers to publish their datasets autonomically. One way to achieve this is to [become a data publisher through GBIF](#). In this way, you

will become the custodian of your own data and will be the best way to give your organisation the proper credit and attribution for the data shared through the GBIF network.

4. How does LIFE RIPARIAS handle personal information?

The LIFE RIPARIAS partners have a legitimate interest to collect, process and publish information regarding the occurrence of invasive alien species (IAS) to support scientific research and policy. Beyond that, we collect the minimum amount of personal information needed. In the [LIFE RIPARIAS privacy policy](#), we describe what personal data we process, and how / why we process this data. We refer to the legal basis for processing and the rights conferred to natural persons.

5. What to do with non-validated data?

The response to this question is simple: the choice to publish non-validated data is up to the data provider. In the dataset published on GBIF, we always foresee a Darwin Core field specifying the validation status of the records (see table below). In case an observation is taken by an experienced observer (e.g. field managers), this observation is considered automatically to be “validated by experts”. In this case our suggestion would be to publish all data points. If the observation is taken by an inexperienced observer, an extra validation step is needed and the validation status should be clearly indicated in the dataset. For the early warning system generated in the LIFE RIPARIAS project, **only validated records will be considered**. However, it might be useful to publish non-validated data as well and let the data user decide whether or not these data points are informative. In this case, sufficient context should be provided in the metadata and the validation status of these records should be stated as “unverified”.

6. What information should your data include?

In the table below, we give an overview of the fields required to share observations of invasive alien species. It is very useful to share more information if you have so in your source database. A detailed overview of the Darwin Core terms to report on species occurrences can be found here or you can get in touch with us (damiano.oldoni@inbo.be, lien.reyserhove@inbo.be) for help or advice. For each required field, we give a short description and suggest a format on how to deliver the information. We encourage you to adopt these suggestions as this simplifies the standardisation process to Darwin Core and reduces the risk of errors.

Special attention should be given to the **observation identifier**. This identifier is unambiguously linked to a specific observation record in the dataset. Such an identifier is especially useful in case your observation is updated or improved: it helps you to unambiguously identify that specific observation at all times. The observation identifier should have the following characteristics:

- each observation must have an identifier
- that identifier must be **unique** within the dataset
- identifiers are never reused: after a record is deleted, its associated identifier is gone forever
- the identifier is **stable**: the same observation will always keep the same identifier, even if some of its fields get updated/improved.

If you already have unique identifiers for your occurrences, please use those. If you don't have them, assign one now so that we can unambiguously reference a given observation henceforth.

Required fields	Description	Suggested format	Example
Observation identifier	A unique identifier for the observation record in your dataset.	Any combination of letter and numbers (and possibly other characters, but no spaces, accents, ...), but see main text body for further specifications.	123456 d430cdc0-38ae-417b-ab91-31975f77e79f
Scientific name	Scientific name of the observed species	full scientific name, with or without authorship	Impatiens glandulifera
Kingdom	The scientific name of the kingdom in which the species is classified	full scientific name	Animalia Plantae Fungi
Date of observation	The date (and time) the observation was made. For datetimes, use UTC timezone.	yyyy-mm-dd yyyy-mm-ddThh:mm:ssZ	2021-10-01 2021-10-01T14:50:00Z
Latitude (for point locations)	The geographic latitude of the observation in WGS84 datum.	decimal degrees, point as a separator	50.503887
Longitude (for point locations)	The geographic longitude of the observation in WGS84 datum.	decimal degrees, point as a separator	4.469936
Location (polygon or line locations)	The geospatial shape (polygon or line) of the observation in WGS84 datum.	Well-Known Text (WKT) representation of the shape, see https://www.wikiwand.com/en/Well-known_text_representation_of_geometry and https://arthur-e.github.io/Wicket/sandbox-gmaps3.html	POLYGON(10 20, 11 20, 11 21, 10 21, 10 20)
Coordinate uncertainty	The distance from the latitude and longitude describing the smallest circle containing the location.	Distance in metres. Leave empty if uncertainty is unknown or cannot be estimated. Do not use zero.	30 (GPS lower limit after 2020-05-01) 100 (GPS lower limit before 2020-05-01)
Quantification of invasion	The number or enumeration value for the quantity of organisms.	Number of individuals Densities Abundance Biomass Cover Leave empty if not known	15 3

Quantification unit	The unit in which the quantification is expressed.	Number of individuals Densities Abundance Biomass Cover Leave empty if Quantification of invasion is not provided	Individuals plants/m ³ % kg
Validation status	An indicator of the extent to which the taxonomic identification has been validated.	If the record was registered by non-experienced observer, choose between: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - unverified - approved by experts - approved on knowledge rules - approved on photographic evidence If the record was registered by experienced observers, use "approved by experts"	unverified approved by experts approved on knowledge rules approved on photographic evidence
Sampling protocol	Through what action was this observation obtained?	casual observation targeted monitoring	casual observation